

Review

Fish toxicity testing for identification of thyroid disrupting chemicals[☆]ZhiChao Dang^{a,*}, Maria Arena^b, Aude Kienzler^b^a National Institute for Public Health and the Environment A. van Leeuwenhoeklaan, 93720, BA, Bilthoven, the Netherlands^b European Food Safety Authority Via Carlo Magno 1/A, 43126, Parma, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Identification of endocrine disruptor/endocrine disrupting chemical
Thyroid disruptor
Fish HPT axis
Zebrafish/medaka/fathead minnow

ABSTRACT

Identification of thyroid disrupting chemicals (TDCs), one of the most studied types of endocrine disruptors (EDs), is required according to EU regulations on industrial chemicals, pesticides, and biocides. Following that requirement, the use of fish as a unique non-mammalian model species for identification of EDs may be warranted. This study summarized and evaluated effects of TDCs on fish thyroid sensitive endpoints including thyroid hormones, thyroid related gene expression, immunostaining for thyroid follicles, eye size and pigmentation, swim bladder inflation as well as effects of TDCs on secondary sex characteristics, sex ratio, growth and reproduction. Changes in thyroid sensitive endpoints may reflect the balanced outcome of different processes of the thyroid cascade. Thyroid sensitive endpoints may also be altered by non-thyroid molecular or endocrine pathways as well as non-specific factors such as general toxicity, development, stress, nutrient, and the environmental factors like temperature and pH. Defining chemical specific effects on thyroid sensitive endpoints is important for identification of TDCs. Application of the AOP (adverse outcome pathway) concept could be helpful for defining critical events needed for testing and identification of TDCs in fish.

1. Introduction

Identification of thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals (THSDCs or TDC, thereafter refer to TDCs), one of the most studied types of endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs), is required by the European Union (EU) legislation on industrial chemicals (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and restriction of Chemicals, REACH, EC, 1907/2006), Plant Protection Products (PPPs, Regulation, EC 1107/2009), and biocide products (BP, Regulation, 528/2012, EC, 2017a). Currently, this identification is mainly based on test results of amphibian and mammalian assays (ECHA/EFSA, 2018). Mammalian tests are included in the core or standard data requirement of these regulations primarily for hazard identification and risk characterisation to humans. The same data package is, additionally, used for hazard assessment and EDC identification of wild mammals. In contrast, amphibian tests are generally not included in the standard data requirements, except the recently revised data requirement for biocides and Regulation 283/2013 laying down the data requirements for PPP active substances. Instead, fish is the main vertebrate species for aquatic toxicity testing and fish toxicity tests are included in the standard requirement of all aforementioned regulations. Current identification of EDCs for the

environment or non-target organisms is mainly based on the results of fish tests. However, the most used chronic fish study, early life stage test according to OECD test guideline (TG) 210, provides little information on endocrine properties of a chemical in general.

Identification of EDCs currently focuses on EATS (estrogen, androgen, thyroid and steroidogenesis) modalities (ECHA/EFSA, 2018). Compared to chemicals with disrupting EAS modalities in fish, much less attention has initially been paid to chemicals disrupting the thyroid modality. This may be due to the following reasons. Firstly, reproductive toxicity was the initial focus of EDCs, with a direct link to the EAS modalities. In contrast, the direct role of the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis in fish reproduction is unclear and there have been very few studies available (Blanton and Specker, 2007). Secondly, among over 25,000 species of fish, the majority of research on the HPT axis in fish has been focused on the limited number of teleost fish species, with the initial attention to salmonids and other species that are of importance to aquaculture (Blanton and Specker, 2007; Yamano, 2005). Information on the fish HPT axis is available only for some species but rather limited or absent for others. Great difference exists in the HPT axis among different species, which makes it difficult to measure and interpret changes in thyroid activity

[☆] This paper has been recommended for acceptance by J Jiayin Dai.

* Corresponding author. National Institute for Public Health and the Environment A. van Leeuwenhoeklaan, 93720, BA, Bilthoven, the Netherlands.

E-mail address: zhichao.dang@rivm.nl (Z. Dang).

(Blanton and Specker, 2007). Thirdly, compared to EAS modalities, the thyroid modality is much more complex. Multiple levels of the thyroid cascade should be considered, including the components of the central control of brain-pituitary-thyroid and the peripheral control of T3 production and metabolism as well as the post receptor-mediated effects of T3 on target cells (Fig. 1). Fourthly, fish species initially used for studying effects of TDCs were often different from those used in test guidelines, with small model fish including zebrafish, medaka, fathead minnow and stickleback as main test guideline species for screening and testing of EDCs (OECD, 2018). In the last decade, small model fish became popular models in developmental biology, biomedicine, and (eco)toxicology because they are readily available, easily cultured, have relatively short life cycles, and respond to chemicals in a similar way as mammals (Raldua et al., 2012; Dang and Kienzler, 2019). Great progress has been made in understanding the physiology of the HPT axis and in developing assays with thyroid sensitive endpoints in these species.

The thyroid gland in fish, in contrast to the compact, encapsulated thyroid gland in mammals, consists of rather diffusely scattered follicles in the region ventral to the pharynx, along the ventral aorta. Heterotopic thyroid follicles in fish have been reported in different tissues including head/trunk kidney, heart, spleen, liver, oesophagus, and brain (Brown et al., 2004; Blanton and Specker, 2007; OECD, 2007). Iodine deficiency is common for terrestrial vertebrates because of iodine deficiency in soil and diet. In contrast, fish take up iodine not only from dietary but also from water via gills. Iodide uptake in gills plays a dominant role and can satisfy most thyroid demand in fish (Brown et al., 2004; Eagles, 2019). Iodide levels in fish plasma are much higher than normal human levels (Brown et al., 2004). Different from mammals and amphibians with the thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) and corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) as the principal regulators of pituitary thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH, or thyrotropin), respectively, the thyrotropic role of TRH

and CRH remains equivocal in fish and may differ greatly among fish species (De Groef et al., 2006; Geven and Klaren, 2017).

Compared to amphibians, fish are a more commonly used model for studying effects of TDCs in the literature (Couderq et al., 2020). There have been increasing literature data showing that chemicals disrupt different targets of thyroid signalling and function in fish. For example, the biologically active form T3 is derived from T4 in the peripheral tissues of fish. The conversion mainly occurs in liver, brain, kidney and gill, with T3 generated by the liver entering circulation. Effects occurring in peripheral tissues, e.g. a change in deiodinase activity, may not necessarily cause disruption of THs in the circulation but can alter TH availability at a local level (Boas et al., 2012). An increase in T4 synthesis does not necessarily signal an increase in the production of T3 (Blanton and Specker, 2007). Changes in TH levels reflect complex biological processes including at least synthesis in the thyroid gland and biotransformation in the peripheral tissues.

Identification of TDCs is based on three essential elements, adversity, thyroid activity or mode of action (MOA) and the plausible link between adversity and the underlying MOA (ECHA/EFSA, 2018). Adversity for non-target organisms or for the environment is based on population relevant adverse effects, which are the outcome of legally required fish standard tests and literature studies. Testing for thyroid MOA is not included in the standard fish toxicity tests. Literature studies are an important source for identification of TDCs (ECHA/EFSA, 2018). Due to the complexity of the HPT axis, results of TDCs on thyroid sensitive endpoints like THs may reflect the outcome of several mechanisms of the thyroid cascade (Brown et al., 2004). Using such data is not straightforward for identification of TDCs. This paper intends to evaluate the publicly available fish data on the effects of TDCs, and to discuss the regulatory use of these data for identification of TDCs.

Fig. 1. Outline of the hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis in fish. The thyroid axis includes the central control of the HPT axis for thyroid hormone (TH) production, the peripheral control of T3 (triiodothyronine) production and metabolism, and the post-receptor-mediated effects of T3 on target cells. Fish take up iodine from dietary and water via gills. Thyroid follicles are responsible for the trapping of iodine via a sodium-iodide symporter (NIS) and producing thyroglobulin (TG). Iodine incorporates into TG, in which thyroperoxidase (TPO) plays a critical role. The synthesis and release of T4 (thyroxine) and T3 in the thyroid follicles are controlled by thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH, or thyrotropin) produced by the pituitary. The principle regulator of TSH is thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) or corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), which varies with fish species. The major binding proteins in fish are transthyretin (TTR) and albumin (Alb). THs are metabolized by different pathways: glucuronidation, sulfation, and deiodination. Thyroid hormones are activated and deactivated by deiodinases (DIOs), which are present in organs like brain, kidneys, gills, and liver. Mono-carboxylate transporter 8 (MCT8) is one of the thyroid hormone transporters which facilitate cellular uptake and efflux of both T3 and T4. THs bind to and activate thyroid hormone receptor (THr) in different organs like swim bladder, eye and reproductive organs to induce thyroid related effects.

2. Literature search

Small model fish, zebrafish (*Danio rerio*), medaka (*Oryzias latipes*), fathead minnow (*Pimephales promelas*) and stickleback (*Gasterosteus aculeatus*) are the focus here. These are the test species of the available TGs or guidance for EDCs (OECD, 2018). Publications were first searched from PubMed by using keywords 'thyroid' in combination with 'zebrafish' or 'medaka' or 'fathead minnow', or 'stickleback', resulting in 462, 43, 31 and 88 papers for zebrafish, medaka, fathead minnow, and stickleback, respectively. They were further selected by exposure to chemicals or mixtures. Papers identified in the initial search were used for retrospective search of additional studies. Studies of different exposure routes, i.e. water, diet, and injection, and studies reporting exposure as nominal or measured concentrations were all included. Both guideline and non-guideline studies published in the literature were included. Data quality of these publications was considered based on the description of fish, life stages of exposure, and test methods. Information on thyroid sensitive endpoints was extracted and further compiled based on the life stages and exposures to chemicals. Thyroid related gene expression and thyroid hormone levels have been studied in both early and late life stages of fish in the literature. Papers compiled here were only for early life stages (Table 1). Papers on thyroid responsive organs including the thyroid gland, eye, and swim bladder were compiled on the basis of life stages that were considered to be sensitive to thyroid activity. These periods are often in the early life stages of fish in which these organs were formed (Tables 2 and 3). Data compiled on sex ratio, secondary sex characteristics, growth, and reproduction in the other tables were an extension of our former work focusing on TDCs (Dang, 2016; Dang and Kienzler, 2019). Another source of data is the EDSP (Endocrine Disruptor Screening Program) database (US EPA, 2015). Chemicals considered to have potential to interfere with the thyroid modality in both humans and non-target organisms were selected. These chemicals were tested according to the OECD TG229 and TG 210 and data quality was considered acceptable.

3. Effects of TDCs on fish

3.1. Effects of TDCs on fish early life stages

Thyroid hormones (THs) are present at all developmental stages and play a critical role in regulating essential biological functions such as embryogenesis, metamorphosis, development, growth, and reproduction in fish (Power et al., 2001; Blanton and Specker, 2007; Walpita et al., 2010; Vergauwen et al., 2018). Different from marine flatfish that must undergo metamorphosis with distinctive larval stages, zebrafish and other small model fish undergo more phenotypically subtle metamorphoses and do not have dramatic morphological reorganization and tissue remodeling that could be readily distinguished as metamorphosis (Parichy and McMenamin, 2013). In the embryonic and larval stages of zebrafish, tissue remodeling events, e.g. development of the cranial cartilages and inflation of the swim bladder, are akin to those of metamorphosis of marine flatfish (Liu and Chan, 2002). THs are critical for these remodeling events in small model fish. There has been increasing papers focusing on the effects of TDCs on fish in the early life stages. These studies have often exposed fish on the basis of the ontogeny profiles of the thyroid gland and thyroid sensitive organs like eyes and swim bladder. According to the EU Directive 2010/63/EU on protection of animals used for scientific purposes (EC, 2010), non-feeding post-hatched embryos are not defined as protected and, therefore, do not fall into the regulatory frameworks dealing with animal experimentation. Pre-hatched zebrafish usually from 0 to the period of 48 and 72 h post fertilization (hpf) and post-hatched embryos or cleutheroembryos before 120 hpf fall into this non-protected animal category (Dang et al., 2017; Sobanska et al., 2018). These embryonic and developmental stages of zebrafish cover the formation periods of thyroid follicles and therefore attract much attention to studying the effects of TDCs. For

example, immunostaining assay is performed by using zebrafish embryos and larvae till 120 hpf (Raldúa and Babin, 2009; Thienpont et al., 2010; Rehberger et al., 2018). Besides, exposure to TDCs has been extended to larvae or juvenile stages beyond 120 hpf in which the formation of thyroid responsive organs, e.g. swim bladder, is complete. Responses of thyroid sensitive organs may reflect thyroid disruption at multiple molecular targets, such as inhibition of T4 production, and inhibition of deiodination of T4 to T3 in peripheral tissues (Power et al., 2001; Orozco and Valverde, 2005; Blanton and Specker, 2007; Marelli et al., 2017). Incorporation of these endpoints into the existing fish test guidelines is currently being explored under EU and OECD projects e.g. the EURION cluster (Holbech et al., 2020).

3.1.1. Thyroid related gene expression and thyroid hormones

Fig. 2 shows the timing of differentiation of thyroid related gene expression in zebrafish. The thyroid hormone receptor (TR) and the monocarboxylate transporter 8 (MCT8) genes begin expression in zebrafish embryos about 3 hpf. The gene expression of deiodinase 1 and 2 (dio1 and dio2) is detectable from 8 hpf. The expression of these genes is long before the embryonic thyroid follicle forms (Darras et al., 2011). The thyroid gland originates from the endoderm layer. Essential transcription factors for thyroid primordium development include haematopoietically expressed homeobox (hhx), thyroid transcription factor-1 (nkx2.1a), and paired box DNA-binding domain (pax) 2/5/8 (Wendl et al., 2002; Heijlen et al., 2013; Porazzi et al., 2019). The expression of nkx2.1a and pax2a appears at 24 hpf in zebrafish; whereas the expression of hhx and pax8 starts at 28 hpf. Up to 30 hpf, the zebrafish thyroid anlage is morphologically characterized as a monolayer sheet of epithelial cells, and first signs of the budding process can be seen at about 32 hpf. The mRNA expression of thyroglobulin (tg) and sodium iodine symporter (slc5a5) are detectable from 32 to 40 hpf, respectively (Porazzi et al., 2019). The gene expression of TSH receptor (tshr) and thyroid peroxidase (tpo) becomes detectable between 40 and 42 hpf. Budding of the thyroid from the pharyngeal epithelium is completed by 48 hpf, and first follicular structures are formed by 55 hpf. The thyroid gland starts to produce T4 at 72 hpf (Porazzi et al., 2009; Heijlen et al., 2013). Chemical induced changes in the thyroid related gene expression are often considered as indication of thyroid disruption (Brown et al., 2004; Blanton and Specker, 2007).

Effects of TDCs on thyroid related gene expression were compiled for 26 chemicals (Table 1). These studies focused on gene expression of different targets of the HPT axis. These targets include transcriptional factors essential for thyroid formation (nkx2.1a, hhx, pax8), the regulators of the HPT axis (crh, trh, tsh), TH synthesis (tpo, tg, slc5a5, nis), transport (ttr, mct8), action (tra, trβ), deiodination (dio1, 2, 3) and degradation (ugt1). Six chemicals have been reported at least twice (Table 1). Studies on the same chemicals reported different results of gene expression. For example, BDE induced a decrease in tshβ in one study but did not change the expression of the same gene in another study (Chan and Chan, 2012; Parsons et al., 2019).

Fish eggs contain a substantial amount of maternal THs that are gradually depleted as the embryo develops (Power et al., 2001; Yamano, 2005; Heijlen et al., 2013). Due to the small size, collecting blood from embryos and larvae is not feasible. Whole-body measurement of THs is often carried out. The amount of THs and the ratio of T4 to T3 in eggs vary among species, with higher concentration of T4 than T3 in freshwater fish (Yamano, 2005). Levels measured in zebrafish eggs are in the ranges of 0.1–0.2 ng/g for T3 and 0.3–2.7 ng/g for T4 (Heijlen et al., 2013). The whole-body content of T4 and T3 in zebrafish is relatively stable before hatching. After hatching, the whole-body content of T4 and T3 rapidly rises, with a peak for T4 at 5 d post-fertilization (dpf) and for T3 at 10 dpf (Heijlen et al., 2013). Changes in TH levels are often used as an indicator of thyroid disruption in fish. Interpretation of these TH data, however, is not straightforward (Brown et al., 2004; Blanton and Specker, 2007) because of the complex physiological processes for thyroid synthesis, secretion and biotransformation. Additionally,

Table 1
Effects of TDCs on thyroid hormones and on expression of thyroid related genes.

Reference	chemical	concentrations (µg/L)	exposure (dpf)	total T4, T3	thyroid related gene expression
Chan and Chan (2012)	BDE-47	2.03, 5.08, 10.2, 15.2 mg/L	0–4		nis ↑, tg ↔, tpo ↔, TRα ↔, TRβ ↔, ttr ↔, tshβ ↓
Chan and Chan (2012)	BDE-47	0.54, 1.34, 2.69, 4.03 mg/L	4–8		nis ↔, tg ↓, tpo ↑, TRα ↑, TRβ ↓, ttr ↓, tshβ ↓
Parsons et al. (2019)	BDE-47	1, 5, 10, 50, 100 µM	0–4		crh ↔, tshβ ↔, tshr ↔, ttr ↔, pax8 ↑, tra ↔, trβ ↑, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↑, dio3 ↑, ugt1ab ↑
Dong et al. (2013)	BDE-47	1, 10, 100 nM	0–1		Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↑, Dio3 ↑
Wang et al. (2019)	BDE-209	0, 2.9, 9.6, 28.8, 95.9, 287.8	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, tshr ↑, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↑, dio3a ↑, dio3b ↑, ttr ↑, tra ↑, trβ ↑, mct8 ↑, ugt1ab ↑
Chen et al. (2012)	BDE-209	0.08, 0.38, 1.92 mg/L	0–14	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, pax8 ↑, nkx2.1 ↑, nis ↑, tg ↑, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↑, tra ↑, trβ ↑, ttr ↓, ugt1 ↓
Tu et al. (2016)	bifenthrin	1, 3, 10	0–3	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, ugt1ab ↑, ttr ↑, tpo ↓, tg ↓, pax8 ↑, nkx2.1 ↓, tra ↑, trβ ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↑
Lee et al. (2019)	bisphenol A	0.08, 0.4, 2, 10 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↑, T4 ↔	crh ↔, tshβ ↔, tshr ↔, pax8 ↔, nkx2.1 ↔, hhxet ↓, tpo ↔, tg ↑, tra ↑, trβ ↔, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↔, ugt1ab ↑ ttr ↑
Chan and Chan (2012)	bisphenol A	0.52, 1.31, 2.62, 3.93 mg/L	0–4		nis ↑, tg ↔, tpo ↔, TRα ↔, TRβ ↔, ttr ↔, tshβ ↔
Chan and Chan (2012)	bisphenol A	0.8, 2.01, 4.02, 6.03 mg/L	4–8		nis ↑, tg ↔, tpo ↔, TRα ↔, TRβ ↔, ttr ↔, tshβ ↑
Tang et al., 2015	bisphenol AF	5, 50, 500	0–7	T3 ↓, T4 ↓	tra ↓, trβ ↓, tshβ ↑, slc5a5 ↓, tg ↑, ttr ↑, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↑
Huang et al. (2016)	bisphenol F	0.2, 2, 20, 200	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↓, TSH ↑	crh ↑, nis ↑, ttr ↓, tg ↑, dio2 ↑, ugt1ab ↑
Lee et al. (2019)	bisphenol F	0.08, 0.4, 2, 10 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↔, T4 ↑	crh ↔, tshβ ↔, tshr ↔, pax8 ↔, nkx2.1 ↔, hhxet ↓, tpo ↔, tg ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↔, ugt1ab ↑ ttr ↔
Zhang et al. (2017)	bisphenol S	0, 1, 3, 10 and 30	0–7	T3 ↓, T4 ↓, TSH ↑	crh ↑, Pax8 ↑, slc5a5 ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↓, Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↑, UGT1ab ↑, Dio3 ↔, TRα ↔, TRβ ↔
Lee et al. (2019)	bisphenol S	0.08, 0.4, 2, 10 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↑, T4 ↔	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, tshr ↑, pax8 ↔, nkx2.1 ↔, hhxet ↓, tpo ↑, tg ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↔, ugt1ab ↑ ttr ↑
Lee et al. (2019)	bisphenol Z	0.04, 0.18, 0.68, 2.9 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↔, T4 ↔	crh ↔, tshβ ↑, tshr ↔, pax8 ↔, nkx2.1 ↔, hhxet ↔, tpo ↔, tg ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↔, ugt1ab ↔ ttr ↔
Yu et al. (2010)	DE-71	0, 1, 3, 10	0–14	T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, Pax8 ↑, slc5a5 ↑, tg ↑, tpo ↔, Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↑, UGT1ab ↑, ttr ↓, nkx2.1 ↑, TRα ↔, TRβ ↔
Wang et al. (2019)	DBDPE	0, 2.9, 9.7, 29.1, 97.1, 291.4	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↑	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, tshr ↓, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↓, dio3a ↓, dio3b ↓, ttr ↓, tra ↑, trβ ↑, mct8 ↑, ugt1ab ↓
Jia et al. (2016)	DEHP	40, 100, 200, 400	0–7	T3 ↑, T4 ↑	crh ↑, tsh ↑, nis ↔, pax8 ↔, nkx2.1 ↑, tg ↑, dio2 ↔, dio2 ↑, ugt1ab ↓, ttr ↑, tra ↔, trβ ↔
Liang et al. (2015)	difenoconazole	0.25, 0.5, 1 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↔, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, ttr ↑ tg ↔, nis ↔, dio1 ↓, dio2 ↑, tra ↔, trβ ↑, ugt1ab ↑
Yu et al. (2013)	hexaconazole	0.625, 1.25, 2.5 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, ttr ↑, UGT1ab ↑, NIS ↑, TG ↔, Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↑, TRα ↑, TRβ ↑
Yan et al. (2012)	microcystin-LR	0, 100, 300, 500	0–4	T3 ↓, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, CRH ↑, NIS ↑, tg ↑, tra ↑, trβ ↓, Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↓
Zhai et al. (2014)	MEHP	0, 1.6, 8, 40, 200	0–7	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, Nkx2.1 ↑, Pax8 ↑, NIS ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↓ Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↑, UGT1ab ↑ trβ ↔
Guo and Zhou (2013)	pentachlorophenol	1, 3, 10	0–14	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, nis ↑, dio1 ↑, dio2 ↑, dio3a ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↑, tra ↑, trβ ↑, ugt1ab ↑, ttr ↔
Liu et al. (2013)	PTU	0.3, 3 and 30 mg/L	0–5		nis ↑, tg ↑, crh ↔, tshβ ↔, tshr ↔, trh ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↔
Baumann et al. (2016)	PTU	50, 100, 250 mg/L	0–5		tsh ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↑, dio3 ↓, tra ↓, trβ ↓, tpo ↑
Zhu et al. (2018)	T3	20	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↔, trβ ↔
Wang et al. (2013)	T3	30	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, Pax8 ↑, slc5a5 ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↔, Dio1 ↔, Dio2 ↔, UGT1ab ↔, hhxet ↔, nkx2.1 ↔
Zhu et al. (2018)	T3+TBBPA	200	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↔, trβ ↔
Yu et al. (2013)	tebuconazole	1, 2, 4 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, ttr ↑, UGT1ab ↑, NIS ↑, TG ↔, Dio1 ↔, Dio2 ↑, TRα ↔, TRβ ↑
Zhu et al. (2018)	TBBPA	50, 100, 200, 400	0–6	T3 ↓, T4 ↑	tshβ ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↓, trβ ↓
Baumann et al. (2016)	TBBPA	100, 200, 300, 400	0–5		tsh ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↔, dio3 ↔, tra ↑, trβ ↔, tpo ↓
Parsons et al. (2019)	TBBPA	0.18, 0.46, 0.92, 1.38, 2.7 µM	0–5		crh ↔, tshβ ↔, tshr ↔, ttr ↔, pax8 ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↔, dio3 ↔, ugt1ab ↔ ttr ↔
Chan and Chan (2012)	TBBPA	0.11, 0.27, 0.55, 0.82 mg/L	0–4		NIS ↑, tg ↔, tpo ↔, TRα ↑, TRβ ↔, ttr ↔, tshβ ↓
Chan and Chan (2012)	TBBPA	0.53, 1.32, 2.64, 3.95 mg/L	4–8		NIS ↑, tg ↔, tpo ↔, TRα ↑, TRβ ↔, ttr ↑, tshβ ↑
liu et al. (2011)	triadimefon	0.5, 1, 2, 4 mg/L	0–5	T3 ↓, T4 ↑	tshβ ↑, dio1 ↓, dio2 ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↓
Dong et al. (2018)	triclocarban	13, 44, 133, 148	0–5	T3 ↔, T4 ↓	dio1 ↑, nis ↑, tpo ↓, tshβ ↔, tshr ↔; tshr2 ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↔, tg ↔, trh ↔, dio2 ↔
Li et al. (2019)	triphenyltin	1, 10, 100 ng/L	7–21	T3 ↔, T4 ↓	crh ↑, tshβ ↑, tg ↑, nis ↑, dio1 ↓, dio2 ↓, tra ↓, trβ ↓
Wang et al. (2013)	TDCPP	0, 10, 50, 100, 300, 600	0–6	T3 ↑, T4 ↓	tshβ ↑, Pax8 ↑, slc5a5 ↑, tg ↑, ttr ↔, Dio1 ↑, Dio2 ↑, UGT1ab ↑, hhxet ↑, nkx2.1 ↑
Tu et al. (2016)	λ-cyhalothrin	1, 3, 10	0–3	T3 ↔, T4 ↑	crh ↔, tshβ ↔, ugt1ab ↔, ttr ↑, tpo ↔, tg ↔, pax8 ↑, nkx2.1 ↔, tra ↔, trβ ↔, dio1 ↔, dio2 ↓

Dio, denio; hhxet, haematopoietically expressed homeobox; MCT8, monocarboxylate transporter 8; NIS, sodium/iodide symporter; PAX, paired box DNA-binding domain; slc5a5, sodium iodine symporter; TF, thyroid follicle; TG, thyroglobulin; TPO, thyroid peroxidase; TR, thyroid hormone receptor; TSHR, thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor.

2,2',4,4'-tetrabromodiphenyl ether (BDE-47), decabromodiphenyl ethane (DBDPE), Di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), mono-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), propylthiouracil (PTU), tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), Tris(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCPP), ↑ increase; ↓ decrease; ↔ no change.

Table 2
Immunostaining for thyroid follicles of zebrafish.

Reference	chemical	target	immuno-T4 staining
Raldua and Babin (2009)	amiodarone	Cytotoxic for thyrocytes	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	pyrazole	Cytotoxic for thyroid gland	↓
Raldua and Babin (2009); Thienpont et al. (2011)	1,1-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroethane (4,4'-DDT)	Increased TH metabolism	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	1,2,3,6,9,10-hexabromocyclododecane (HBCD)	Increased TH metabolism	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	2,2',4,4'-tetrabromodiphenyl ether (BDE-47)	Increased TH metabolism	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	pentabromobiphenyl ether (BDE-209)	Increased TH metabolism	↔
Raldua and Babin (2009); Jomaa et al., (2014)	T3	inhibition of TSH	↓
Raldua and Babin (2009)	atrazine	negative control	↔
Raldua and Babin (2009)	fenoxycarb	negative control	↔
Li et al. (2012)	potassium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	↓
Li et al. (2012)	potassium thiocyanate	NIS inhibitor	↓
Esalini et al. (2003); Alt et al. (2006); Thienpont et al. (2011)	potassium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	potassium thiocyanate (KSCN)	NIS inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	sodium bromide (NaBr)	NIS inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	sodium nitrate (NaNO ₃)	NIS inhibitor	↔
Raldua and Babin (2009)	2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)	TDC	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	3,3',5,5'-tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA)	TDC	↓
Raldua and Babin (2009)	4-nonylphenol (4-NP)	TDC	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	benzophenone-3 (BP3)	TDC	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	heptadecafluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS)	TDC	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	linuron	TDC	↔
Raldua and Babin (2009)	methylmercury (MeHg)	TDC	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	pentadecafluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	TDC	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	2-imidazolidinethion (ethylenethiourea, ETU)	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	amitrole	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	benzophenone-2 (BP2)	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	bisphenol A (BPA)	TPO inhibitor	↔
Thienpont et al. (2011)	genistein	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	mancozeb	TPO inhibitor	↓
Elsalini et al. (2003); Alt et al. (2006);	methimazole (MMI)	TPO inhibitor	↓

Table 2 (continued)

Reference	chemical	target	immuno-T4 staining
Raldua and Babin (2009); Thienpont et al. (2011); Jomaa et al., (2014); Rehberger et al. (2018); Li et al. (2012)	phloroglucinol	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	phenylthiourea	TPO inhibitor	↓
Elsalini et al. (2003); Alt et al. (2006); Li et al. (2012)	propylthiouracil	TPO inhibitor	↓
Raldua and Babin (2009); Thienpont et al. (2011); Rehberger et al. (2018)	resorcinol	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	sulfamethoxazole (SMX)	TPO inhibitor	↓
Thienpont et al. (2011)	2,3-dihydropyridine (DHP)	TPO inhibitor	↓
Li et al. (2012)	resorcinol (RES)	TPO inhibitor	↓

↓ decrease; ↔ no change; TDC, thyroid disrupting chemicals; thyroid peroxidase (tpo), sodium iodide symporter (NIS).

interpretation of TH data is generally problematic for animal models due to e.g. circadian rhythms and technical problems with the different measurement methods (Martin et al., 2020; Wheeler et al., 2021).

As shown in Table 1, effects of TDCs on total levels of THs were compiled for 24 chemicals. All studies reported the effects on T3 and T4 levels. In addition, two studies reported also the effects on TSH (Huang et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2017). Different effects of bisphenol F on THs in zebrafish were reported in two studies (Huang et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2019). Remarkably, an increase in T3 and a decrease in T4 were observed in zebrafish exposed to bisphenol F at the concentration of 0.2 mg/L till 6 dpf; whereas no changes in T3 and an increase in T4 were reported in zebrafish exposed to bisphenol F at the concentration of 2 mg/L till 5 dpf (Huang et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2019). No discussion was provided for the different results in the original studies. It is noted that test concentration ranges overlapped and the similar enzyme-linked immunoassay (ELISA) methods was used for the TH measurement in these two studies. The opposite effects on T4 in zebrafish exposed to bisphenol F may not be due to the difference in the treatment periods because the levels of T3 and T4 are stable between 5 and 6 dpf (Chang et al., 2012). Similarly, bisphenol S at the concentration of 30 µg/L decreased both T3 and T4 levels in zebrafish exposed till 7 dpf (Zhang et al., 2017); whereas bisphenol S at the concentration of 50 mg/L increased T3 but had no changes in T4 in zebrafish exposed till 6 dpf (Lee et al., 2019). No discussion and explanation were provided for the difference in the test concentrations and in the responses in the original two studies (Zhang et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2019).

3.1.2. Zebrafish eleutheroembryo bioassay

The fish thyroid gland produces iodine-containing thyroid hormones triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4). This organ is often studied by using histological staining and immunostaining. Immunostaining for thyroid follicles of zebrafish has been considered as a useful tool to screen potential TDCs (Raldua and Babin, 2009; Thienpont et al., 2010; Rehberger et al., 2018). This assay is often performed by using zebrafish

Table 3
Effects of chemical on fish swim bladder.

Reference	fish	chemical	exposure (hpf)	concentrations (mg/L)	posterior bladder
Liu and Chan (2002)	ZF	T3	0–120	5 nM	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	T3	0–144	10 nM	↓
Molla et al. (2019)	ZF	T3	0–9	5 nM	↑
Molla et al. (2019)	ZF	IGF-1Rb	0–9	1 mg/L	↔
Molla et al. (2019)	ZF	T3+IGF-1Rb	0–9	5 nM + 1 mg/L	↔
Godfrey et al. (2019)	MD	T3	0–10	10 nM	↑f, ↓m
Liu and Chan (2002)	ZF	T4	0–120	10, 30 nM	↓
Liu and Chan (2002)	ZF	amiodarone	0–120	50 nM	↔
Jomaa et al. (2014)	ZF	amiodarone	0–120	0.01 mM	↓
Liu and Chan (2002)	ZF	amiodarone + methimazole (MMI)	0–120	50 nM + 0.3 mM	↓
Stinckens et al. (2020)	ZF	iopanoic acid (IOP)	0–120	0.35, 1	↓
Jomaa et al. (2014)	ZF	sodium perchlorate	0–120	0.025–0.4 mM	↓
Stinckens et al. (2020)	ZF	6-propylthiouracil (PTU)	0–120	37, 111	↓
Stinckens et al. (2016)	ZF	2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT)	0–120	0.1, 0.35, 0.56, 0.7, 0.88, 1.75, 3.5, 7	↔
Stinckens et al. (2020)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–120	50, 100	↔
Liu and Chan (2002)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–120	0.3, 1 mM	↔
Jomaa et al. (2014)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–120	0.25 mM	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–144	30 nM	↔
Elsalini and Rohr (2003)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–120	15 mM	↓
Godfrey et al. (2019)	MD	methimazole (MMI)	0–10	30 nM	↑f, ↓m
Nelson et al. (2016)	FM	2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT)	0–144	0.25, 0.5, 1	↔
Macaulay et al. (2015)	ZF	6-hydroxy-2,2-x0003_4,4-x0003_-tetrabromodiphenyl ether (6-OH-BDE-47)	0–144	10–250 nM	↓
Raldúa et al. (2008)	ZF	clofibrate	0–7	0.1, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 5 mg/L	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	0–144	1%	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	heptafluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	0–144	1%	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCPP)	0–144	1%	↓
Godfrey et al. (2019)	MD	tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCPP)	0–10	1%	↑f, ↓m
Shi et al. (2008)	ZF	perfluorooctane sulphonate potassium salt (PFOS)	0–168	0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5	↓
Li et al. (2011)	ZF	tris (2,3-dibromopropyl) isocyanurate (TBC)	0–120	0.5, 1, 2.5, 5, 10 µg/L	↓
Hagenaars et al. (2011)	ZF	perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	0–120	10, 25, 50, 100, 250, 500	↓
Godfrey et al. (2019)	MD	perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	0–10	1%	↑f, ↓m
Hagenaars et al. (2011)	ZF	perfluorooctane sulphonate potassium salt (PFOS)	0–120	1, 5, 10, 25, 50, 100	↓
Hagenaars et al. (2011)	ZF	heptafluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	0–120	50, 100, 250, 500, 1000, 3000	↓
Godfrey et al. (2019)	MD	heptafluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	0–10	1%	↑f, ↓m
Hagenaars et al. (2011)	ZF	perfluorobutane sulfonate (PFBS)	0–120	50, 100, 250, 500, 1000, 3000	↓
Hagenaars et al. (2014)	ZF	perfluorooctane sulphonate potassium salt (PFOS)	0–144	0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 5, 10, 25, 50, 100	↓
Shi et al., 2019	ZF	6:2 chlorinated polyfluorinated ether sulfonate (F–53 B)	0–5	5, 50, 500 µg/L	↓
Dong et al. (2018)	ZF	triclocarban	0–5	13, 44, 133, 148 µg/L	↓
Yue et al. (2015)	ZF	2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (TCDD)	0–4	1 ng/ml	↓
liu et al., 2011	ZF	triadimefon	0–5	0.5, 1, 2, 4 mg/L	↓
Reference	fish	chemical	exposure (dpf)	concentrations (mg/L)	anterior bladder
Stinckens et al. (2020)	ZF	iopanoic acid (IOP)	0–32	0.35, 1	↓
Stinckens et al. (2020)	ZF	6-propylthiouracil (PTU)	0–32	37, 111	↓
Stinckens et al. (2016)	ZF	2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT)	0–32	0.1, 0.35, 0.56, 0.7, 0.88, 1.75, 3.5, 7	↓
Nelson et al. (2016)	FM	2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT)	0–14	0.25, 0.5, 1	↓
Stinckens et al. (2020)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–32	50, 100	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	methimazole (MMI)	0–28	30 nM	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)	0–28	1%	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	heptafluorobutanoic acid (PFBA)	0–28	1%	↓
Godfrey et al. (2017)	ZF	tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCPP)	0–28	1%	↓

IGF-1 receptor (IGF-1R) blocking peptide (IGF-1Rb); f, female; m, male; FM, fathead minnow; MD, medaka; ZF, zebrafish.

embryos and larvae till 5 dpf or 120 hpf and this technique may be useful for other fish species with small thyroid glands that are difficult to remove for quantitative measurement of THs. As the thyroid follicle is formed at 55 hpf (Alt et al., 2006), and starts to produce T4 at 72 hpf (Elsalini et al., 2003), this timing of 4 or 5 dpf for immunostaining occurs after the complete formation of thyroid follicles. Different exposures have been reported in the literature including continuous exposure from embryos (0–120 hpf) in which thyroid follicle is formed and from eleutheroembryo of 48–120 hpf after the formation of thyroid follicles. Therefore, the former reflects effects of TDCs on thyroid follicle development/formation and its function; whereas the latter indicates only

effects of TDCs on thyroid function (Raldúa and Babin, 2009, Thienpont et al., 2010; Rehberger et al., 2018). Immunostaining for thyroid follicles of zebrafish has been studied by using different antibodies detecting epitopes of thyroglobulin (Alt et al., 2006), T4 (Elsalini and Rohr, 2003; Alt et al., 2006; Raldúa and Babin, 2009, Thienpont et al., 2010; Jomaa et al., 2014; Rehberger et al., 2018), and T3 (Rehberger et al., 2018). The staining patterns are similar for these antibodies in control zebrafish. When zebrafish were exposed to chemicals, however, different patterns of thyroid follicle staining of these antibodies have been observed. Phenylthiourea, methimazole, and potassium perchlorate all decreased T4-immunostaining but did not change thyroglobulin-staining. These

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of timing of differentiation of thyroid related endpoints in zebrafish. Numbers indicate hours post fertilization (hpf). d, days; Dio, deiodinases; hhhex, haematopoietically expressed homeobox; MCT8, monocarboxylate transporter 8; PAX, paired box DNA-binding domain; Slc5a5, sodium iodine symporter; TF, thyroid follicle; TG, thyroglobulin; TPO, thyroid peroxidase; TR, thyroid hormone receptor; TSHR, thyroid-stimulating hormone receptor.

results suggest that thyroglobulin staining occurs independently of thyroglobulin iodination (Alt et al., 2006). Another study showed that propylthiouracil increased and decreased the number of T4- and T3-immunostained follicles, respectively; but decreased fluorescence intensity of T4- and T3-immunostaining (Rehberger et al., 2018). As shown in Table 2, this type of assays can detect chemicals directly targeting the thyroid gland including those causing cytotoxicity to thyrocytes (amiodarone and pyrazole), sodium iodide symporter (NIS) inhibitors (potassium perchlorate, potassium thiocyanate, and sodium bromide), and TPO inhibitors (ETU, BP-2, genistein, mancozeb, methimazole, phloroglucinol, PTU, resorcinol and sulfamethoxazole). However, these assays may not consistently detect chemicals that influence TH metabolism (4,4'-DDT, HBCD, BDE-47 and BDE-209). Inhibitory effects were observed for TBBPA, 4,4'-DDT, 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, and 4-nonylphenol; no effects were reported for BP-3, PFOS, PFOA, linuron, HBCD, BDE-47, BDE-209, atrazine, fenoxycarb, sodium nitrate, methylmercury, and bisphenol A (Raldua and Babin, 2009; Thienpont et al., 2010; Jomaa et al., 2014; Rehberger et al., 2018). Interestingly, T3 showed a decrease in immunostaining, suggesting an inhibitory effect of T3 via a secondary feedback mechanism (Raldua and Babin, 2009). Effects of the NIS inhibitor sodium nitrate and the TPO inhibitor bisphenol A were considered as false negatives; effects of TBBPA and 4,4'-DDT were considered as false positives because of the presence of systemic toxicity at high concentrations (Thienpont et al., 2010). These results suggest that concentration-dependent data are very useful in interpretation of the assay results. Overall, such assays quantify intrafollicular contents of THs as an indirect measurement of TH synthesis. A decrease in the content of T3 or T4 indicates chemicals inhibiting thyroid function or having an antithyroid effect. However, the results do not indicate the particular molecular target of a chemical of interest, i.e., specific or nonspecific, direct or indirect (Raldua and Babin, 2009). Besides, the assays cannot detect chemicals that stimulate the thyroid function. Currently, zebrafish eleutheroembryo thyroid assay has been included in the JRC EURL ECVAM validation program. An alternative to immunostaining of fish thyroid follicles has been proposed with the use of transgenic zebrafish embryo model, which allows to screen TDCs by measuring gene reporter fluorescence. This transgenic fish model is time and cost effective and has potential for fast and automated screening of TDCs (Jarque et al., 2018).

3.1.3. Thyroid related organ—eye

Zebrafish eye development begins at around 14 hpf and is complete at approximately 72 hpf, with the phototransduction fully functional at 5 dpf (Gestri et al., 2012). There are four cone photoreceptors responsible for color vision in zebrafish: red, green, blue, and UV. Zebrafish became red colorblind when *trp2* was knocked out, and the photoreceptor patterning shifted to the other three cone types (Deveau et al., 2020). Knockdown of both activating (D1, D2) and inactivating (D3) deiodinases led to morphological defects including reduced eye size, disturbed retinal lamination and strong reduction in rods and all four

cone types; as well as disruption of visual function. These results suggest that THs play an important role in eye development (Bagci et al., 2015; Houbrechts et al., 2016; Deveau et al., 2020). Changes in eye morphology and function are used as endpoints for the effects of TDCs in fish (Baumann et al., 2016; Molla et al., 2019; Reider and Connaughton, 2014). T3-treated zebrafish showed increased eye development (Molla et al., 2019); whereas PTU, MMI, 2,3-dihydroxyppyridine (DHP), resorcinol, and TBBPA decreased eye size (Baumann et al., 2016; Molla et al., 2019; Reider and Connaughton, 2014; Li et al., 2012). It has been further shown that T3-increased eye size was abolished by the IGF-1 receptor (IGF-1R) blocking peptide (IGF-1Rb), suggesting the involvement of this pathway in eye development (Molla et al., 2019). Interestingly, PTU-inhibited eye size was not rescued by adding T3 or T4 or, 3,3', 5-triiodothyroacetic acid (TriAc), a thyroid hormone analogue (Li et al., 2012). The NIS inhibitors, potassium perchlorate and potassium thiocyanate, did not change eye size (Li et al., 2012). These results show that TPO inhibition rather than a general suppression of thyroid hormone synthesis is likely the underlying cause of PTU-induced reduction of eye size (Li et al., 2012). Besides, PTU, T3, IOP and BDE-47 reduced eye pigmentation (Macaulay et al., 2015; Baumann et al., 2016); whereas TBBPA did not change eye pigmentation (Baumann et al., 2016). Molecular pathways of the eye development were further studied by using microarray analysis in PTU- and TBBPA-exposed zebrafish (Baumann et al., 2019). The results showed that genes of repair and regeneration processes, associated with a general metabolic activation were changed (Baumann et al., 2019). Overall, the available evidence indicates that TDCs influence eye development. However, not all thyroid mediated mechanisms of action may produce effects on eye development and other pathways, e.g. IGF, may be involved in the eye development and eye function.

3.1.4. Thyroid related organ—swim bladder

The swim bladder or air bladder is a gas-filled sac consisting of posterior and anterior chambers (Robertson et al., 2007; Winata et al., 2009). The main function of this organ is to control buoyancy. Besides, it functions as a resonating chamber to produce or receive sound. Due to its vital importance in fish health, swim bladder was initially studied in aquaculture species. Changes in swim bladder were linked to maternal nutrition, water temperature, and disinfectants in aquaculture (EC, 2017b). In the last decade, more attention has been paid to small model fish and the effects on swim bladder have been linked to developmental toxicity and thyroid disruption (Jomaa et al., 2014; Knapen et al., 2020). In zebrafish, the swim bladder arises from an outgrowth of the foregut endoderm (Winata et al., 2009). The posterior chamber is first visible just after hatching as a fluid-filled sac, which is then filled with air and inflates between 1 and 3 dph (Robertson et al., 2007). At around 20 dpf, the anterior chamber starts to inflate (Winata et al., 2009). The mechanism of swim bladder development and inflation is not known. However, the formation of swim bladder coincides with metamorphosis, which is regulated by THs. Molecular data of knockdown, knockout and

rescue of the TH-related genes show that THs play an important role in the development and inflation of the swim bladder (Liu and Chan, 2002; Heijlen et al., 2014; Knapen et al., 2020).

As shown in Table 3, exposure of newly-fertilized zebrafish embryos for 5 or 6 dpf to T4 or T3 led to a delay or lack of inflation of the posterior bladder (Liu and Chan, 2002; Jomaa et al., 2014; Godfrey et al., 2017). These results are different from the observations in zebrafish reported by Molla et al., (2019), in which T3-induced inflation of the posterior bladder was reported (Molla et al., 2019). It is noted that TH induced effects on the posterior bladder in these studies used comparable concentrations of THs. The opposite results could not be explained on the basis of two publications. Methimazole, a thyroid peroxidase (TPO) inhibitor, did not influence inflation of the swim bladder even at the toxic concentration of 1 mM, which caused severely stunted growth, retarded head cartilage development and pair fin elongation, curled tails (Liu and Chan, 2002; Jomaa et al., 2014; Stinckens et al., 2020). In two other studies, delay of inflation and absence of swim bladder were observed in zebrafish exposed to methimazole at 2 and 15 mM, which may be related to general toxicity (Elsalini and Rohr, 2003; Jomaa et al., 2014). Similarly, another TPO inhibitor, 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT), did not directly impair posterior chamber inflation and did not affect the surface of the posterior chamber in zebrafish and in fathead minnow (Nelson et al., 2016; Stinckens et al., 2016, 2020). Furthermore, iopanoic acid (IOP) and 6-propylthiouracil (PTU), two deiodinase inhibitors; sodium perchlorate, an inhibitor of sodium iodide symporter (NIS), and amiodarone, an antagonist of TRs, deflated swim bladders in zebrafish (Jomaa et al., 2014; Stinckens et al., 2020). Delay or lack of inflation of the swim bladder in zebrafish was reported for industrial chemicals, pesticides, biocides, and pharmaceuticals (Table 3). These include 6-hydroxy-2,2,4,4-tetrabromodiphenyl ether (6-OH-BDE-47), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulphonate potassium salt (PFOS), heptafluorobutanoic acid (PFBA), perfluorobutane sulfonate (PFBS), 6:2 chlorinated polyfluorinated ether sulfonate (F-53 B), tris (1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate (TDCPP), tris(2,3-dibromopropyl) isocyanurate (TBC), TCDD, triadimefon, and clofibrate (Shi et al., 2008; Li et al., 2011; Hagens et al., 2014; Macaulay et al., 2015; Godfrey et al., 2017; Yue et al., 2015). Some of the studies reported that it is unclear whether delay or lack of inflation of swim bladder is associated with thyroid disruption (Shi et al., 2008; Hagens et al., 2011, 2014, 2014; Godfrey et al., 2017). Besides, the clofibrate-induced delay or lack of inflation of swim bladder is the results of mechanical pressure due to embryonic malabsorption syndrome with very little yolk consumption (Raldúa et al., 2008) and the TCDD-induced delay or lack of inflation of swim bladder was secondary to heart failure (Yue et al., 2015).

In summary, different mechanisms of action of TDCs including THs, antagonists of TRs, NIS inhibitors, TPO inhibitors and perfluorinated chemicals that may target metabolic processes, have been studied for their effects on posterior chamber inflation in zebrafish, medaka and fathead minnow (Table 3). Exposure of zebrafish to these chemicals were similar, starting from newly-fertilized embryos to at least 120 hpf. Their effects, however, are different. A lack of effect on posterior inflation has been explained by maternal transfer of T4 into the eggs. T3, the biologically active form which is present at 120 hpf, may derive from deiodination of maternally T4. The observation that knockdown of deiodinases and an exposure to deiodinase inhibitors led to an impairment of posterior chamber inflation in zebrafish supports this hypothesis (Bagci et al., 2015; Stinckens et al., 2016, 2020, 2020). However, this hypothesis may not explain different effects of the aforementioned chemicals. There may be other mechanisms, e.g. IGF-1 (Molla et al., 2019), developmental toxicity (Raldúa et al., 2008; Yue et al., 2015), involving in the development and inflation of posterior chamber. General toxicity and embryonic toxicity may also interfere with inflation of posterior bladder.

Different from a lack of effect on posterior chamber, TPO inhibitors, methimazole and MBT exposure impair anterior chamber inflation in zebrafish and fathead minnow (Nelson et al., 2016; Stinckens et al.,

2016; Godfrey et al., 2017). In addition, deiodinase inhibitors, IPO and PTU, also impaired anterior chamber inflation (Stinckens et al., 2020). Industrial chemicals, PFOS, PFBA, and TDCPP, deflated anterior bladder in zebrafish (Godfrey et al., 2017). Overall, these results suggest that chemicals targeting different thyroid mechanisms impair anterior bladder inflation in zebrafish and fathead minnow (Table 3). Currently, the adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) for the thyroid pathways in relation to anterior and posterior swim bladder have been developed by OECD. Expert reviews have been just finished. It is expected that these AOPs will be adopted by OECD in the near future. Several papers have been published for these AOPs and their application (Nelson et al., 2016; Stinckens et al., 2018; Knapen et al., 2020).

3.2. Effects of TDCs on sex ratio and secondary sex characteristics

Sex ratio in fish is an important endpoint of several OECD test guidelines including the Fish Sexual Development Test (FSDT, TG234), the Medaka Extended One-Generation Reproduction Test (MEOGRT, TG240) and the draft Zebrafish Extended One-Generation Reproduction Test (ZEOGRT). This endpoint is considered as a population relevant endpoint as well as an endpoint indicating EAS activity (OECD, 2018; Dang and Kienzler, 2019). Interestingly, sex ratio can be changed by TDCs too (Dang, 2016; Dang and Kienzler, 2019). This paper explores whether TDCs can change sex ratio in fish. As shown in Table 4, T4 induced male biased sex ratio in zebrafish (Sharma and Patiño, 2013; Sharma et al., 2016). In contrast, in the same species, perchlorate, an inhibitor for NIS, induced female biased sex ratio (Mukhi et al., 2007a; Sharma and Patiño, 2013) or has no effect on sex ratio (Schmidt et al., 2012). In sticklebacks, perchlorate induced hermaphroditism/male biased sex ratio (Bernhardt et al., 2006; Furin et al., 2015). The difference in perchlorate-induced sex ratio in zebrafish may be due to the window of exposure and timing of analysis of gonad morphology (Schmidt et al., 2012). Two other NIS inhibitors, nitrate and nitrite, did not change sex ratio in zebrafish (Bjerregaard et al., 2018). The difference in male or female skewed sex ratio may also be related to different species. Effects of TPO inhibitors methimazole and genistein on sex ratio were studied in zebrafish and medaka, respectively. Methimazole induced female biased sex ratio in zebrafish exposed between 3 and 33 dpf (Sharma and Patiño, 2013); whereas genistein did not change sex ratio in medaka (Kiparissis et al., 2003). It has also been observed that a female biased sex ratio was observed at 45 dpf but not at 60 dpf in zebrafish exposed to methimazole between 3 and 33 dpf (Sharma and Patiño, 2013). This difference may result from the different depurations in these two experiments. Methimazole induced female biased sex ratio was not reversed after a short period of depuration <15 days (observation at 45 dpf), but was reversed after a long period of depuration (observation at 60 dpf) (Sharma and Patiño, 2013; Dang and Kienzler, 2019). As shown in Table 4, several TDCs including o, p'-DDT (Edmunds et al., 2000), PFAAs (Lee et al., 2017), PFOS (Du et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2011), tetrabromobisphenol A (Chen et al., 2016; Kuiper et al., 2007) and tribromophenol (Deng et al., 2010) changed sex ratio in zebrafish and in medaka. Among these studies on sex ratio, PFOS, for example, changed sex ratio in zebrafish in one study (Wang et al., 2011) but not in another study (Du et al., 2009). This difference may result from different exposure periods in which one study was not long enough (Dang and Kienzler, 2019). The mechanisms of TDC action on fish sex ratio are uncertain. However, it has been proposed that TDCs may directly or indirectly target gonadal aromatase, a key enzyme regulating gonadal sex (Sharma et al., 2016). Effects of thyroid disruption on sex ratio or gonad maturation may also be indirectly influenced by TDC-induced delay of development and growth. There is also a cross-talk between the HPT, HPG and HPI, which may lead to direct or indirect effects on sex ratio (Cortes et al., 2014; Dang, 2014).

Overall, effects of TDCs on sex ratio in different fish species are not consistently observed. Chemicals with the same mechanisms of action influenced sex ratio differently. The direction of sex bias due to an

Table 4
Effects of chemical on fish sex ratio.

Reference	Fish	Chemical	target	concentrations (µg/L)	exposure (dph)	Depuration	Method for determining sex	Effects on sex ratio
González-Doncel et al., 2016	MD	BDE-47	Increased TH metabolism	10, 100, 1000 ng/g	4-40 dph	60 d	SSC	no difference in sex ratio
Thornton et al., 2016	FM	BDE-47	Increased TH metabolism	57.68; 392.59 µg/g	6-34 dpf	34 dpf - 9 months	SSC	female-biased sex ratio
Teather et al., 2005	MD	chlorothalonil		0.06	0-7 dph	5 month	SSC/gonad inspection	female biased sex ratio
Han et al. (2013)	ZF	DE-71	Increased TH metabolism	5 ng, 1 µg, 50 µg/L	0-120 dpf		gonad inspection	male biased sex ratio
Kiparissis et al. (2003)	MD	genistein	TPO inhibitor	1,10,100, 1000	1-100		histology and SSC	no difference in sex ratio
Sharma and Patino (2013)	ZF	methimazole	TPO inhibitor	0.15, 0.3 mM	3-33 dpf	12 days	histology	female biased sex ratio
Sharma and Patino (2013)	ZF	methimazole	TPO inhibitor	0.15, 0.3 mM	3-33 dpf	27 days	histology	no difference
Sharma et al. (2016)	ZF	methimazole	TPO inhibitor	0.15 mM	3-33 dpf	12 days	histology	female biased sex ratio
Bjerregaard et al. (2018)	ZF	Nitrate (NO ₃ -)	NIS inhibitor	10, 20, 25, 50, 100 mg/L	20-60		histology	no difference
Bjerregaard et al. (2018)	ZF	Nitrate (NO ₃ -)	NIS inhibitor	10, 20, 25, 50, 100 mg/L	0-60		histology	no difference
Bjerregaard et al. (2018)	ZF	Nitrite (NO ₂ -)	NIS inhibitor	5, 20 mg/L	20-60		histology	no difference
Bjerregaard et al. (2018)	ZF	Nitrite (NO ₂ -)	NIS inhibitor	5, 20 mg/L	0-60		histology	no difference
Edmunds et al. (2000)	MD	o,p'-DDT		20, 33, 237, 580, 1079 ng/egg		10 weeks	SSC	86% males to females
Lee et al. (2017)	MD	PFAAs		2, 20 µg/L	TG240 exposure		SSC	male biased sex ratio
Du et al. (2009)	ZF	PFOS		10, 50, 250	14-70 dpf	30 d	gonad inspection	no difference
Wang et al. (2011)	ZF	PFOS		5,50, 250	8-150 dpf		not specified	female biased sex ratio
Schmidt et al. (2012)	ZF	potassium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	62.5, 125, 250, 500 and 5000 µg/L	0-35 dpf		histology	no difference
Bernhardt et al. (2006)	SB	sodium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	30, 60, 100 mg/L	8 months		histology	masculinization
Furin et al. (2015)	SB	sodium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	30, 100 mg/L	1 y		gonadal inspection	masculinization
Mukhi et al. (2007)	ZF	sodium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	100, 250 ppm	3-33 dpf	10 days	histology	female biased sex ratio
Sharma and Patino (2013)	ZF	sodium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	0.82 mM	3-33 dpf	12 days	histology	female biased sex ratio
Sharma and Patino (2013)	ZF	sodium perchlorate	NIS inhibitor	0.82 mM	3-33 dpf	27 days	histology	female biased sex ratio
Mukhi et al. (2007)	ZF	sodium perchlorate + T4	NIS inhibitor + thyroid hormone	100, 250 ppm each + 10 nMT4	3-33 dpf	10 days	histology	male biased sex ratio
Sharma and Patino (2013)	ZF	T4	thyroid hormone	1, 10 nM	3-33 dpf	27 days	histology	male biased sex ratio
Sharma and Patino (2013)	ZF	T4	thyroid hormone	1, 10 nM	3-33 dpf	27 days	histology	male biased sex ratio
Sharma et al. (2016)	ZF	T4	thyroid hormone	2 nM	3-33 dpf	12 days	histology	male biased sex ratio
Sharma et al. (2016)	ZF	T4 + methimazole		2nMT4 +0.15 mM methimazole	3-33 dpf	12 days	histology	male biased sex ratio
Chen et al. (2016)	ZF	tetrabromobisphenol A		5,50 nM	1-120 dpf	4 months	SSC	no difference
Kuiper et al. (2007)	ZF	tetrabromobisphenol A		0.023; 0.047; 0.094; 0.188, 0.375; 1.5 µM	0-47, F1		histology	female biased sex ratio
Deng et al. (2010)	ZF	tribromophenol		0.3, 3	0-120 dpf		gonad inspection	male biased sex ratio
Stenzel et al. (2019)	ZF	triclosan	disrupting biosynthesis of THs	0.4, 4, 40	21-35 dpf	55 days	histology	male biased sex ratio

FM, fathead minnow; MD, medaka; ZF, zebrafish; thyroid peroxidase (tpo), sodium iodide symporter (NIS).

exposure to TDCs may be related to species-specific sex determination mechanisms. Based on the limited number of available studies, it is difficult to draw a general conclusion on the effects of chemicals targeting thyroid mechanisms on sex ratio because these studies used different test designs and test concentrations, which confound the data interpretation of sex ratio influenced by TDCs.

The endpoint secondary sex characteristics (SSCs) is included in the OECD test guidelines for indicating EAS modalities (OECD, 2018). It is based on the visual inspection of external sex specific landmarks

including pigmentation, size, fins, body shape, and visibility of urogenital papilla (Dang and Kienzler, 2019). It has been well established that chemicals disrupting EAS modalities induce changes in SSCs (OECD, 2018; Dang and Kienzler, 2019). Additionally, THs play an important role in regulating SSCs and TDCs can interfere with SSCs. Especially fin development can be seen as a part of metamorphosis (Parichy and McMenamin, 2013), which is sensitive to TDCs. Pigmentation of zebrafish embryos begins to occur around 24 hpf. Knockdown of type 2 iodothyronine deiodinase (D2) reduced embryonic

pigmentation; T3 treatment rescued effects of D2 knockdown (Walpita et al., 2009). Interestingly, T3-treated zebrafish induced a pronounced skin paling in both adult female and male zebrafish; this change was reversible when T3 exposure was stopped. These results suggest that T3 effects on pigmentation may vary with age, which is likely related to a decrease in the number of melanophores after hatching (Guillot et al., 2016). T3 and T4 treatment for two weeks accelerated pelvic fin growth and induced early differentiation of pectoral fins (Brown, 1997). Effects of methimazole and combination of methimazole and T4 on pectoral fin length were studied at 45 dpf of zebrafish which were exposed between 3 and 33 dpf. Pectoral fin length was reduced by exposure to methimazole and rescued by co-administration of T4. This change was not associated with body length. Based on this observation, the authors proposed that a change in pectoral fin length was likely a sensitive and useful morphological marker of TDCs (Sharma et al., 2016). Besides, chronic exposure to waterborne thiocyanate led to concentration dependent effects on SSCs in fathead minnow, with males failing to develop the large fat pad (Lanno and Dixon, 1994). Perchlorate exposure led to nuptial coloration rarely and weakly expressed in male stickleback and the sex of most treated stickleback could not reliably be determined before genetic testing (Bernhardt, 2006). Chemicals considered to have potential to interfere with the thyroid modality in the EDSP (Endocrine Disruptor Screening Program) were tested in fathead minnow according to TG229. Among these 12 TDCs, a decrease in SSC score was observed in 2 chemicals (Dimethoate and Metolachlor). No effects on SSC were observed in 10 TDCs.

In summary, effects of TDCs on SSCs were reported in different fish species. However, only a limited number of fish studies are available on this topic. More studies are needed to elucidate the effects of TDCs targeting different thyroid mechanisms on SSCs.

3.3. Effects of TDCs on growth and reproduction

Growth is an important population relevant endpoint included in several OECD test guidelines, although it is only "sensitive to but not diagnostic of EATS mediated" adversity (ECHA/EFSA, 2018). Effects of TDCs on growth have been reported in different studies in the literature. Exposure of 10-week old juvenile fathead minnows to T3 at concentration of 12.5, 25 and 50 µg/L for 13 weeks led to a decrease in body weight (Abrahams and Pratt, 2000). Fathead minnow exposed to ammonium perchlorate at 10 or 100 mg/L from embryo to 28 dpf resulted in developmental and growth retardation, which were considered as the result of hypothyroidism during the early stages of exposure. Interestingly, thyroid follicular epithelial cell height was changed at the perchlorate concentration of 1 mg/L, more sensitive than changes in delayed development of scales and pigmentation as well as growth at 10 mg/L (Crane et al., 2005). In contrast, hypothyroidism of fathead minnow during the early stages of exposure to methimazole at 32 µg/L from embryo to 84 dpf led to an increase in body length at 28 dpf and 56 dpf but not at 84 dpf (Crane et al., 2006). In a partial life cycle toxicity test, there was a decrease in body length and weight at 42 dph of F1 zebrafish exposed to propylthiouracil (PTU) at the concentration of 100 mg/L (van der Ven et al., 2006; Schmidt and Braunbeck, 2011). Body length and weight of zebrafish exposed to PFOS from 14 dpf to 70 dpf were not affected in females but were reduced in males at 40 and 70 dpf. In this study, PFOS did not alter total T3 levels after exposure for 40 and 70 dpf (Du et al., 2009). Another substance tris (2-butoxyethyl) phosphate decreased T4, without a change in T3, and decreased body weight and length in zebrafish exposed during 20–90 dpf. Based on changes in gene expression of related pathways, the authors suggested that the mechanisms of action of an inhibition of growth induced by this chemical may not be related to the HPT axis (Zeng et al., 2018).

There is mounting evidence that TDCs disrupt reproduction of fish. Several known antithyroidal chemicals have been tested for their influence on fish reproduction. A change in histology of thyroid follicles and no change in reproductive performance were reported in zebrafish

exposed to ammonium perchlorate at concentrations of 18 ppm for 8 weeks. In contrast, at a high concentration of 677 mg/L, perchlorate suppressed spawning activity. The authors concluded that the severe reproductive toxicity of 677 mg/L perchlorate is due primarily to toxic effects but not to thyroid effects because acute mortality was observed upon the initial exposure period and the appetite and activity level of the treated fish were chronically depressed during the whole period of exposure (Patino et al., 2003). In another study, a prolonged exposure of 10 weeks to perchlorate at concentrations of 10 and 100 mg/L was performed, leading to a decrease in T4 but not in T3. Concurrently, egg production was decreased, and the authors concluded that this reproduction effect resulted from T4 homeostasis disruption (Mukhi and Patino, 2007). PTU induced a concentration-dependent increase of egg production with a concomitant decrease of mature oocyte size but had no effect on fertilization rate or hatching in zebrafish (Van den Ven et al., 2006). Sexually differentiated but immature fathead minnows were exposed to thiocyanate at concentrations between 0.06 mg/L to 32.6 mg/L for 124 days, leading to a delay in time of first spawning and decreased fecundity at the concentration of 7.3 mg/L. This effect was considered as thyroid related because no other toxic effect was observed at this concentration. At higher concentrations, that no spawning was observed is considered as toxic effects (Lanno and Dixon, 1994). Zebrafish between 21 and 35 dpf were exposed to triclosan at concentrations of 0.4, 4 and 40 µg/L. A decrease in egg numbers and in fertility was observed in zebrafish exposed to 0.4, and 4 µg/L triclosan. Although thyroid disruption was indicated by a change in morphological biomarkers, relative snout to pectoral distances and relative pelvic to anal fin distance, the authors considered that the reproductive effects at these two concentrations may result from non-thyroid MOA (Stenzel et al., 2019). Chemicals considered to have potential to interfere with the thyroid modality in the EDSP were tested in fathead minnow according to TG229. Among these 12 TDCs (Table 5), a decrease in fecundity was observed in 9 chemicals (carbofuran, chlorothalonil, DCPA (chlorthal dimethyl), dimethoate, metolachlor, PCNB, phosmet, pronamide, and tetrachlorvinphos (TCVP); no effects on fecundity in 3 chemicals (Ethoprop, MGK-264, Propargite).

4. Use of fish testing results in the regulatory context

This paper summarized studies on the effects of TDCs on THs, thyroid related gene expressions, thyroid sensitive parameters like thyroid histology, eye development and phototransduction as well as swim bladder inflation. A change in one of those parameters compared to a control may indicate thyroid activity and/or adversity and can be used for triggering further testing or for drawing a conclusion on whether or not the ED criteria are met for the chemical under assessment (ECHA/EFSA, 2018).

The ECHA/EFSA Guidance (2018) in line with the available test methodology recommends using amphibians as model species for investigating potential EDC through the T-modality and fish for E, A and S modalities. Thanks to the ongoing research projects and the new test methods, in the near future it may be possible to use fish as model species not only for EAS-modalities but also for the thyroid modality. On the one hand this is highly appreciated as it would allow to apply more a 3 R approach in line with Directive 2010/63/EU; on the other hand uncertainties still exist which would need further clarification and consideration both for adversity and for endocrine activity.

Many of the available studies, investigating endocrine activity on fish, use adult life stages. New test methodologies proposing the use of elutheroembryos are under development. Such a kind of innovative methods is considered a good alternative to standard vertebrate testing as elutheroembryos are regarded as a non-protected life stage in some regulatory jurisdictions. Care should be, however, taken when using this kind of methods as elutheroembryos may not be fully developed and metabolic competent and therefore not able to capture all the possible modes of action across the thyroid cascade.

Table 5
Effects of TDCs on fathead minnows in the reproduction test.

chemical	test concentrations (µg/L)	fecundity	fertilization	SSC	VTG	Histology
Carbofuran	44, 140, 435	435↓	140↓	↔	↔	↔
Chlorothalonil	0.074, 0.77, 9.9	9.9↓	9.9↑	↔	↔	↔
Chlorthal-dimethyl (DCPA)	7.4, 22, 58	22↓	58↓	↔	↔	↔
Dimethoate	3.4, 18, 96 mg/L	96↓	96↓	18↓m	↔	↔
Ethoprop	4.6, 19, 91	↔	↔	↔	↔	↔
Metolachlor	46, 480, 4700	4700↓	↔	4700↓m	4700↓f	↑
MGK-264	13, 36, 107	↔	↔	↔	↔	↔
Pentachloronitrobenzene (PCNB)	0.63, 6.9, 74	74↓	↔	↔	↔	↑
Phosmet	1, 9, 105	9↓	9↓	↔	↔	↑
Pronamide	94, 1100, 8300	1100↓	1100↓	↔	↔	↑
Propargite	0.2, 1.8, 18	↔	↔	↔	↔	↑
Tetrachlorvinphos (TCVP)	6, 55, 570	570↓	570↓	↔	570↓	↔

↑ increase; ↓ decrease; ↔ no change, the above data were extracted from the EDSP (Endocrine Disruptor Screening Program) database, LOECs (lowest observed effect concentration) were indicated for each endpoint.

Generally, it is recommended that any new test method should undergo a proper validation by testing an appropriate number of chemicals with different modes of action. This would allow to highlight strengths and limitations of a particular study design. Outcomes of validation exercises help in framing the scope and context in which a particular test method may be used. These are considered key for the implementation of new test methods in regulatory frameworks. Due to the nature of time- and cost-consuming of validation, more funding for validation would be important for the test guideline development.

In view of minimizing vertebrate testing, the ECHA/EFSA guidance recommends starting the assessment with mammals because the dataset is normally extensive and may allow to conclude the ED properties of a chemical. Additionally, even when a conclusion cannot be drawn based on mammalian dataset only, it gives some hints to consider further testing in the assessment of non-mammalian species. To date for the thyroid modality, a lot of knowledge and experience have been gained on how mammals and amphibians may response to TDCs. Due to the lack of T-mediated parameters in fish test guidelines, a similar level of understanding is not available and a comparison between mammals and fish is currently not possible. When fish are introduced to replace amphibians in the ECHA/EFSA testing strategy, it would be important to understand whether fish and amphibians differ in sensitivity to TDCs. Knowledge on interspecies sensitivity in detecting TDCs is, however, scarce since, up to now, limited number of chemicals have been tested in both fish and amphibians. A comparison of responses to TDCs would allow first to detect any potential difference in sensitivity between fish and amphibians, as was done by Pickford (2010) and Dang (2019), between mammals and amphibians. Additionally, such a comparison would clarify whether the differences may be associated with a particular MOA. Although it is well known that the endocrine system is conserved among vertebrates, a lack of data on TDCs tested in fish and in amphibians and mammals would prevent any analysis for understanding to what extent extrapolation between taxa may be possible. For example, while in mammals and amphibians, thyroid histopathology is one of the most sensitive parameters for the identification of TDC, scarce information is available on thyroid histology in fish as not routinely performed in regulatory studies. Even though, measures of vascularization, epithelial cell height, and the T4 colloidal ring can be analysed provided that enough follicles are sampled, the histological examination in fish is intrinsically more complex as the thyroid is not encapsulated but follicles are scattered (Blanton and Specker, 2007).

Changes in T-mediated parameters in non-target organisms are considered adverse when they are relevant at population level, as implied by the Regulation 2018/605. Population relevant effects are changes in parameters that show an expectation of adverse effect on the population in the field. While certain parameters are assumed to be relevant for populations of non-target organisms by default, e.g. reproductive parameters, for others, e.g. delay in time to metamorphosis, eye development, swim bladder inflation, etc., this association may not be so

direct. Although many of the above mentioned parameters are crucial for preventing predation, for example, the interpretation on the population relevance may depend on the severity and degree of the observed effects. Furthermore, any change at organ level like a change in thyroid histopathology in isolation is not considered relevant for the maintenance of the population of wildlife. Therefore, a key aspect to consider in the development of new test method or enhancement of existing ones is the inclusion of apical parameters that, when clearly affected, are considered relevant at population level.

The assessment of the relevance at population level is not the only key aspect for the identification of T-mediated adversity. According to the Regulation 605/2018, a substance should not be considered a TDC when T-mediated adversity is secondary to systemic toxicity. Endocrine homeostasis including the thyroid may be influenced by non-specific factors including stress, nutrient, and the environmental factors like temperature and pH (Brown et al., 2004; Dang, 2014; Mihaich et al., 2017). Dose dependent analysis as well as consideration on the Maximum Tolerated Concentration (MTC) are important for distinction of thyroid adversity from general toxicity. Tests under development should allow to discriminate between a primary T-MOA and systemic toxicity. When systemic toxicity may be excluded and changes are observed in fish thyroid sensitive endpoints, it may be challenging to understand the underlying MOA due to the lack of test guidelines for the investigation of the endocrine activity through the T-modality.

Currently, several adverse outcome pathways (AOP) that are relevant to fish and the thyroid pathway have been proposed and are under development. Examples of how the AOP framework and associated data generation for addressing fish thyroid disruption have been published (Nelson et al., 2016; Stinckens et al., 2018; Noyes et al., 2019; Knapen et al., 2020). Information on these AOPs is useful for consideration of plausibility of adversity and thyroid activity, and might give additional information on the species applicability domain of these AOPs. In the regulatory context, however, only limited data are available.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Small model fish like zebrafish, medaka, fathead minnow and stickleback are used for screening and testing of endocrine disrupting chemicals. These fish species are also used for studying effects of TDCs on thyroid sensitive endpoints in the literature. These endpoints include THs, thyroid related gene expressions, thyroid histology, eye opening and development and swim bladder inflation as well as external sex specific landmarks like pigmentation and fins. Effects of TDCs on growth, sex ratio and reproduction, were also evaluated. All these endpoints are important for identification of TDCs by addressing adversity and/or thyroid activity. Our main conclusions and recommendations are summarized as follows.

1. TH homeostasis in fish involves complex physiological processes, including iodine uptake, TH synthesis and storage in the thyroid gland, release of THs into and transport through the circulation, cellular TH transport, tissue-specific TH deiodination and degradation of THs by catabolic hepatic enzymes, and the central regulation of the HPT axis (Fig. 1). No single thyroid sensitive endpoint examines all facets of the thyroid cascade. Some of the thyroid sensitive endpoints have been studied by testing more chemicals; others by only a limited number of chemicals. The applicability domain of these thyroid sensitive endpoints has not yet been defined. Future studies should focus on testing chemicals targeting different processes of the thyroid cascade in order to define the applicability domain of thyroid sensitive endpoints.
2. Generally, it is recommended that an appropriate number of chemicals targeting different mechanisms of the thyroid cascade in different taxa should be selected for the validation of a new fish thyroid test guideline. Robust validation is crucial for the acceptance of new test methods in the regulatory context. This would allow to highlight strengths and limitations of a particular study design. Outcomes of validation exercises help in framing the context in which a particular study may be used and for which scope and this is considered key for the implementation of new test methods in regulatory frameworks.
3. Changes in thyroid sensitive endpoints may reflect the balanced outcome of different processes of the thyroid cascade. They may also be regulated by non-thyroid molecular or endocrine pathways. In addition to chemical exposure, these changes may be influenced by non-specific factors including general toxicity, stress, development, nutrient and environmental factors. Defining chemical specific effects on thyroid sensitive endpoints is important for identification of TDCs.
4. Thyroid sensitive endpoints measured at the gene, cell, organ and tissue level provide insights into thyroid activity of a chemical. These endpoints are not considered adverse as they are not population-relevant endpoints in the regulatory context for identification of TDCs. The outcome of these thyroid sensitive endpoints indicates thyroid activity and can be used for triggering further testing and for drawing a conclusion on whether or not the ED criteria are met for the chemical under assessment
5. Population relevant apical endpoints growth, sex ratio and reproduction, are considered as “sensitive to, but not diagnostic of, EATS” for identification of TDCs. A MOA analysis is needed to establish the plausibility between adversity and the underlying thyroid activity. Changes in thyroid sensitive endpoints may not indicate a particular molecular target of a chemical of interest, leading to a difficulty in further testing on the basis of the available AOPs. There is a great challenge for the MOA analysis because of the limited information available in the regulatory context. Application of the AOP concept to the MOA analysis should be further explored to define critical information needed for identification of TDCs in fish.

Disclaimer

The publication was drafted under the sole responsibility of the authors. The positions and opinions presented are those of the authors alone and are not intended to represent the views of the institutions they work for.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Peter Van Vlaardingen from RIVM for the critical reading and suggestions. The Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management is acknowledged for funding this work (project number M/260100/21/SM).

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